

A Phenomenological Study of Academic Challenges Faced By Children With Specific Learning Disability (Sld)

□ Arpeeta Anand*

Dr. Mohd. Fajjullah Khan**

ABSTRACT

Specific Learning Disability (SLD) is a neurological problem which creates lots of challenges in the life of children. Academic challenges are the most significant one when it comes to SLD. **Aims:** To realize the academic challenges that children experienced with Specific Learning Disability. **Setting and Design:** Phenomenological method with purposive sampling technique was used to understand the perspective of children. **Materials and Methods:** Semi-structured Interview Schedule was administered on 10 SLD children who are already diagnosed by clinical psychologist studying in elementary grade i.e. 6th grade to 8th grade of private inclusive schools of Delhi. **Analysis Used:** Content Analysis was used to elicit the data from open-ended questions. **Results:** (i) Children with learning disability are not lazy & dumb, they perceive and process information in a different manner. (ii) They encounter difficulty in comprehending what they have read, experience making mistakes while reading, repeating the sentences, taking pause, trouble in remembering & mispronouncing same sounding words. (iii) Children doesn't want to write because of the fright behind committing spelling mistakes. (iv) Many children experience problem of illegible writing, pain in hand, extra efforts & longer time for writing and trouble in expressing their own ideas & feelings in writing. (v) They struggle while comprehending & solving the word problems, issues of learning formulas, making things in order of operations, basic calculations, understanding time, directions, money related work and difficulty in keeping scores of games & matches. (vi) Have trouble in adjusting to new situations, take time to adapt new changes in their life, demand lots of coordination & organization, face problem in rote learning & remembering, comprehending meaning from text and thinking out of box (vii) Complained about inability to perform activities that require sequential order, meeting deadlines, following schedules, arranging things, setting priorities and managing time for themselves. (viii) Experience inability to interpret their own environment as a consequence react inappropriately, misunderstood situation and comprehend different meaning with incorrect interpretation. (ix) Trouble in understanding what they hear and making differences in sound, difficulty in comprehending meaning from sounds, require frequent repetition and struggle in remembering what they heard. (x) The foremost problem of misunderstanding in analyzing and synthesizing visually presented information. (xi) They experience inability to differentiate between same sounding words, struggle while copying from writing board, mispronouncing the words while reading, difficulty in comprehending meaning out of what they read and figuring out what is there in pictures & graphs. **Conclusions:** The present study has identified various challenges faced by children academically. Proper support & motivation of parents & teachers can help children in developing positive attitude towards learning.

Keywords: *Specific Learning Disability, Children, Education, Academic Challenges, Phenomenological Analysis*

* Ph.D. Scholar, Assistant Professor of Special Education (Learning Disability)
Department of Teacher Training & Non-Formal Education, Faculty of Education, Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi

life (Lerner, 2000). It lead slow development of academic skills and ability to learn new concepts in children which somehow lead to school failure (Stanovich, 1986). In view of the fact, children lack behind because of continuous failure. This result into school dropout (Rutter, 1978).

As per the U.S. Department of Education (2001), Learning disabled children are at high risk of dropping out. Data revealed around 70% children with SLD fail to graduate from high school. These children also shows lower engagement in post-secondary schooling and employment (Murray, Goldstein, & Edgar, 1997). Hence, it is critical to improve academic outcome and address the academic achievement of children with SLD.

Children with Specific Learning Disability have difficulty in reading, spelling, writing and mathematics (Student Support Services, 1992). These children usually experience problem of distraction, lack of coordination and time management skills. Moreover, they are challenged with understanding and following directions. (Student Advising and Learning Center, 1992). It has been found difficulty with reading words, comprehension, mathematical calculation and problems applied are associated with academic profiles of learning disability (Crompton, 2012). Because the attention–concentration is poor, the child may need many repetitions in order to process the information. Children with learning problems experience difficulty in solving a task, organizing activities, making corrections and approaching towards conclusion (Kohli, Malhotra, Mohanty, Khehra & Kaur, 2005).

Children with mathematical deficit experience difficulty while telling time, comprehending mathematical concepts & formulas and struggle semantic memory retrieval (Burny and Desoete, 2012). Data revealed that around 6% school going children undergo challenges with arithmetic and it's processing. Children with Developmental Dyscalculia found with

deficit in their cognitive system which hampers their number processing (Christophe, Mejcas & Noel, 2010). Children with mathematical disability experience conceptual problem while analyzing, thinking abstractly and performing reasoning whereas students having low achievement in mathematics have less translational errors and more computational errors (Hartmann, 2007).

Individuals with learning disabilities use less complex sentence structures, incorporate fewer ideas, produce poorly organized paragraphs and write less complex stories. Gargiulo (2004) Difficulty in writing, because of lack of coordination of teams of small muscles leading to slow & illegible handwriting, too much slant, space difficulty, poor visual memory, messiness, misspellings, grammatical and semantic errors and letters merging into one another. (Kohli, Malhotra, Mohanty, Khehra & Kaur, 2005)

Reading disability is more over powering in learning disability when compare with any other academic performance. It has been estimated that 60% to 90% students with learning disability have reading disorder. (Bender, 2001) The main issues with reading deficit are reading slowly, word by word reading, taking long pauses, ignorance in punctuation, words omitting and mispronunciation. Children had difficulty with comprehension attributed to poor decoding skills which lead to difficulty in reading. Children had inadequate copying skills and had difficulty with spelling. (Kohli, Malhotra, Mohanty, Khehra & Kaur, 2005)

These children struggle in understanding what they read despite of accurate reading and having normal nonverbal abilities. (Nation, Clarke and Marshall, 2004). Children who had presented delayed language acquisition in preschool performed significantly worse on several measures of verbal efficiency, working memory, and reading and writing tasks compared with

dyslexics without previous language delay. (Chilosi, Larni and Pizzoli, 2003)

Reading disability is a phonological processing problem which impact decoding of words, create cognitive limitation and poor functioning of phonological structure of words. (Torgeson and Wagner, 1998) Poor performance in reading and other academic area affect the student's self-image and confidence. This will also lead to poor motivation with behavioral tantrums. (Polloway, Patton and Serna, 2001)

The struggle in academic domain with SLD lead to social and emotional problems in children (Grolnick & Ryan, 1990). Data revealed that (24 to 52) % children with SLD suffer with social and emotional problem (Rock, Fessler & Church, 1997). Concerns in this domain of social & emotional problem in learning disabled children shed light to many researches (Vaughn & Elbaum, 1999). However, left the state unclear on academic problems faced by children with SLD. To replenish the knowledge gap, this study has been conducted to study academic challenges faced by Specific Learning Disability among elementary school children aged 10-14 years.

Research Methodology

Since the present study aims at studying "Academic Challenges faced by Specific Learning Disabled (SLD) Children", phenomenological method found suitable. The study is qualitative in nature, as the variable for the study are Children with Specific Learning Disability. They were interviewed to enquire about the perspective towards Academic Challenges. Semi-structured interview schedule was used which further elicits the result. Both Primary and Secondary data were used for the present research. Secondary data helped in framing the objectives, understanding previous researches while the Primary data helped in checking the field reality.

Sample

For the purpose of the study, children with SLD already diagnosed by clinical psychologist studying in elementary grade i.e. 6th grade to 8th grade of private inclusive schools of Delhi were interviewed. The sample of 10 children were drawn through the purposive sampling technique. Inclusion criteria included elementary grade children i.e. 6th grade to 8th grade who are already diagnosed as SLD by clinical psychologist and could participate with informed consent of parents and teachers. All those children who was absent on the day of data collection and all those who were not willing to enter the research frame were excluded.

The sample was primarily (40%) of children aged 14 years with minimal (20%) aged 11 years & 13 years and some (10%) belongs to 10 years and 12 years. Out of 10 children, 70% were boys and 30% were girls. With respect to Class/Grade 50% belongs to 8th Grade whereas 30% belong to 7th grade and only 20% belongs to 6th grade. In order to see onset of the problem in child, 0% result was seen within last year, only 10% between 1 to 2 years ago and more than 2 years ago. Majority (50%) has been seen more than 3 years ago and few (30%) with more than 4 years ago. A significant part of the overall sample reported SLD types as per DSM V, 50% disclose they are suffering from Dyslexia, 30% with Dyscalculia and only 20% with Dysgraphia.

Tools

Semi-structured Interview Schedule was developed, to collect the feedback of Children. The content validity of each item in the tool validated by 11 experts working in the same field as per Lawshe formula (1975). All those items having content validity ratio less than 0.59 were excluded from the tool. The suggestions given by experts and after pilot testing on 2 children, tool was modified.

Procedure of Data Collection & Analysis

Interview Schedules would be self-administer, children of already diagnosed specific learning disabled child by clinical

psychologist studying in elementary grade i.e. 6th grade to 8th grade of private inclusive schools of Delhi were interviewed. Firstly, consent from the parents, teachers & children were taken. Rapport was framed with children at the initial phase before starting the interview. The procedure was explained to them. And all their experiences were recorded for further analysis. Content Analysis was used to elicit the data from open-ended questions.

Result

Nine Super-ordinate themes emerged from the participant's accounts. The findings of the study are illustrated with the extracts from the interviews.

Theme 1: Problem in Reading

Reading is an important skill. It gives opportunity to learners to enhance their vocabulary and to know their world. Somewhere, neurological problem hinder many children with language processing which result into reading difficulty. This is illustrated by a girl. She said:

"I am studying in grade 8th ... It is difficult for me to read aloud in class as I make mistakes while reading... I don't know why this happens to me but this gives me embarrassment in front of my class.... my classmates make fun of my reading abilities..."

A boy quoted:

"Reading is challenging task... whenever my teacher tells me to read... though I read with many pauses but I really don't understand what I generally read... I told the same thing to my teacher but she never understands..."

This issue was supported by another boy. He expressed:

"I don't like reading... I just can't remember the difference of same sounding words... I work hard in learning but I forget... my parents help me in learning but my teacher never supports me... she usually says ...I am good for nothing..."

Theme 2: Problem in Spellings

Spelling is an important competence where letters are used to build words. Children

with spelling difficulty face complexity in writing work which leads to poor performance at school. They avoid using spellings which are complicated because of fear to make mistakes. They may develop negative attitude towards learning. One of the boy claimed:

"I am 11 years old... I love practicing mathematics... it's very interesting... but I don't like any other subjects... for that I need to learn many spellings... I work hard in learning spellings but I fail to remember it... Nobody believes me... they says I lie to them..."

A girl pointed out:

"I don't like giving exams... though I work so hard... but my teacher always cut my marks for spelling mistakes... I left with poor grades... my friends make fun of me... my elder brother also teases me..."

Theme 3: Problem in Writing

Writing is a challenging task. Problem of Writing emerges when a child is introduced to this skill. Generally this skill of writing develops in children at different pace, some learn early as others take longer time. More or less children address the deficit of ineligible writing but few may also experience difficulty while expressing their ideas in writing or both. As illustrated by a boy:

"I dance very well... I want to become dancer in my future... but my parents always scold me when I dance... they tell me to study all the time... I hate studying... because whenever I do my classwork and homework... everybody says I have a bad handwriting... though I erase and try to write neatly... still they says they can't read my writing..."

A girl specified:

"Whenever I write... I feel pain in my hand... it takes me longer time than my peers to finish my classwork..."

This issue is supported by another boy. He highlighted:

"My writing is not good... I write leaving space between words to make it neat... still my writing is bad... my friend writing is so

beautiful... I wish I could also write like her..."

Another boy uncovered:

"I learn many things... I express many things... but whenever I try to write my own ideas & feelings... I am unable to do that... I really don't know why this happens to me... I work really hard but left with poor grades... I get scolding from my parents & teachers for this... they don't understand my hard work..."

Theme 4: Problem in doing Mathematics

Remembering facts of mathematics, rules complexity, long list of formulas, problem-solving steps are not easy to comprehend for everyone. Many children struggle in computing answers quickly and fail to understand mathematical terms. One of the girl who has dyscalculia claimed:

"I study in 7th grade... I love studying... but I don't like mathematics class... I don't understand what my mathematics teacher teaches in class... I hate word problems... I just can't remember formulas and order of operations..."

A boy explained:

"Few things bothers me a lot... Though I am not a bad student... but whenever it comes about mathematics I score very badly.... I just can't manage with numbers... I am poor at calculations... I struggle hard in telling time to someone... I can't keep scores while playing cricket... Though it's my favorite game... I don't understand directions..."

Another boy unveiled:

"Understanding money related work and cash transactions is impossible for me... I feel unable to manage it... Whenever I go for buying anything... I am totally dependent on my family and friends... I am poor at basic calculations... it is a problematic thing to manage money for me... though it seems easy for many but for me is a major challenge..."

Theme 5: Nonverbal learning problems

Nonverbal learning problems are most misunderstood difficulty faced by children. The difficulty in understanding body language, facial expression with poor

spatial, visual and organizational skills became a challenge for teachers and parents. Many children with Nonverbal learning deficit have trouble in recognizing, processing indication and lack in motor efficiency. This is illustrated by a boy. He mentioned:

"I am in 8th grade... my parents changed my school... as I was performing poorly there... but here I don't have any friend... this makes me sad... I miss my old school..."

A girl specified:

"Going school is the thing... I hate the most... I don't like participating in any activities... whether drawing, painting, running, playing basketball... I am unable to perform well in these... my friends teases me... my teacher scolds me... this gives me frustration..."

Another boy proclaimed:

"Geography & Mathematics are subjects which gives me lots of stress... to understand geographical maps is a challenging task for me... It is difficult for me to learn long list of tables & formulas... complexity of these subject somewhere demotivate me towards learning"

Supported by one more boy. He mentioned:

"I face problems in understanding reading comprehension... five out of four answers get wrong while comprehending... I can write essay on simple and familiar topic... but in exams I have very tricky topics... which is difficult for me to imagine and write... this results into poor grades..."

Theme 6: Organizational problems

Procuring success in school and in life, organizational skills work as an essential element. All those children having organizational difficulty need consistent help in arranging things, setting priorities and focusing on time management skills when conduct tasks in school. A girl indicate:

"Whenever I do mathematical questions... I got stuck between the steps... I forget how to prove these steps... remembering step by step calculations and proving the formula in mathematics is tricky for me..."

A boy expressed:

“Completing homework is a difficult task for me... I try hard to finish it but never able to finish it in time... Same with following time table... I prepare it but I can't follow it...”

Another boy disclosed:

“My teachers always complain to my parents... that I am bad in maintaining notebooks... I always leave classwork for tomorrow... never finishes in time... She always complained... I keep my table messy... all books here and there... finding pencils, pens & all are challenging on my table... there is no space on my table for keeping my notebook...because of this I have a bad handwriting...”

Theme 7: Problem in Understanding Social cues

Understanding cues while communicating with others like words of people, their expression and their body language are noteworthy. Children with social cues issues experience difficulty in understanding others and their social situation as a consequence react inappropriately. A girl reported:

“Many a times it happen... when my teacher scolds me for my work or punishes me... I start laughing & smiling... I don't know what happens to me in that situation... I find it very funny... and because of that... my parents also rebuked me...”

A boy mentioned:

“My friends make fun of me... they always say when teacher ask questions... always my answers are out of line... I really don't know... I listen to ma'am very attentively then how can my answers be wrong... and teacher also nod her head... that too I don't understand whether I am right or wrong...”

Theme 8: Auditory Processing Problem

Auditory Processing difficulty is a challenge in understanding while hearing and making differences in sound. In this process brain doesn't support in usual manner. Children with this deficit trouble in comprehending meaning from sounds. This lead to learning delays in children. A boy expressed:

“I don't like my school... I only go there... because I love playing with my friends...

whatever my teacher teaches... I don't understand... she instruct so many things at a time... it is difficult for me to understand what she means out of her conversation...”

Another boy unveiled:

“My friends always make fun... whenever I ask them to repeat what they said... I get confused many a times... sometimes this attitude of my friends left me depressed and sad...”

A girl pointed out:

“My class teacher always motivate me to participate in singing competition... I sang very well but I am bad in remembering the lyrics... so my music teacher never suggest my name for any competition... This make me frustrated... I asked my parents many times... when will I can remember all the lyrics correctly... and get chance to participate... they don't have any answer...”

Theme 9: Visual Processing Problem

Visual Processing difficulty reduces the capability to discern information by seeing. Children with this challenge found complexity with visual information interpretation but they don't have any issue with the sharpness of vision. This create trouble in analyzing and synthesizing visually presented information. This is illustrated by a boy. He specified:

“When I do calculations... the written symbols of addition, subtraction, multiplication, division confuses me... not only this... I generally not able to differentiate between same sounding words... I also struggle while copying from writing board...I don't understand how in future will I overcome this...I score poor grades because of this”

A girl reported:

“Reading accurately without mispronouncing is a dreamlike for me... but whenever I start reading... my classmates start mocking at me... I also feel difficulty in comprehending meaning out of what I read... figuring out what is there in pictures & graphs are also very challenging for me...”

Discussion

The present study sheds light on the academic challenges experienced by children in their journey with specific learning disability. Specific learning disability is a neurological condition which hampers learning in many ways. This deficit has no association with intelligence & motivation. Children with this disorder are not lazy & dumb, the only difference are they perceive and process information in a different manner. Learning Disability lead slow development of academic skills and ability to learn new concepts in children which somehow lead to school failure (Stanovich, 1986). It has been found difficulty with reading words, comprehension, mathematical calculation and problems applied are associated with academic profiles of learning disability (Crompton, 2012). In this study, nine major themes have been identified & discussed; “Problem in Reading”, “Problem in Spellings”, “Problem in Writing”, “Problem in doing Mathematics”, “Nonverbal learning problems”, “Organizational problems”, “Problem in Understanding Social cues”, “Auditory Processing Problem” and “Visual Processing Problem”.

In this study, while taking specific learning disability into frame, it gives insight about the different hindering factors which are associated. Children with Specific Learning Disability have difficulty in reading, spelling, writing and mathematics (Student Support Services, 1992). To accomplish success in life, the skill of reading has significant impact in growing academically. Problem in reading is the most common informed problem by many children when it comes to learning disability. Reading disability is more over powering in learning disability when compare with any other academic performance. It has been estimated that 60% to 90% students with learning disability have reading disorder (Bender, 2001). It's not necessary that every learning disable has same problem. Some encounter difficulty in comprehending what they have

read and other may experience making mistakes while reading, repeating the sentences, taking pause. The main issues with reading deficit are reading slowly, word by word reading, taking long pauses, ignorance in punctuation, words omitting and mispronunciation. Children had difficulty with comprehension attributed to poor decoding skills which lead to difficulty in reading (Kohli, Malhotra, Mohanty, Khehra & Kaur, 2005). Few may face trouble in remembering & mispronouncing same sounding words. Learning Disability is an individualized disorder which requires proper skills to get identified. Because of its hidden nature, sometimes it becomes very difficult in specifying it. Spellings in learning disability plays a key role as many children found spelling deficit. As seen, many school going children experience problem in learning spellings. When it occurs with a reason of learning disability, after hard try children fail in remembering spellings. Children had difficulty with spelling (Kohli, Malhotra, Mohanty, Khehra & Kaur, 2005). This result into poor grades and limit child's vocabulary. Children doesn't want to write because of the fright behind committing spelling mistakes. Somewhere, this result into poor writing skills. The consequences of failure & embarrassment build negative attitude towards learning.

Skill of writing need lots of hard work and practice. When a child is introduced with writing, few grasp the skill early with less labor other might face lots of trouble while learning and mastering the skill. In consequence of writing deficit, many children experience problem of illegible writing, continuous erasing and trying to write neatly, somewhere demotivate & hinder their writing interest. Difficulty in writing, because of lack of coordination of teams of small muscles leading to slow & illegible handwriting, too much slant, space difficulty, poor visual memory, messiness, misspellings, grammatical and semantic errors and letters merging into one another

(Kohli, Malhotra, Mohanty, Khehra & Kaur, 2005). Few complained about pain in hand and demand of extra efforts & longer time for writing. To present their writing as neat, some leave spaces between words. Whereas, others uncovered their trouble in expressing their own ideas & feelings in writing. Individuals with learning disabilities use less complex sentence structures, incorporate fewer ideas, produce poorly organized paragraphs and write less complex stories Gargiulo (2004).

Mathematics is an important subject. It teaches us power of reasoning, how to think with creativity, enhances our abstract & spatial thinking, gives exposure to our critical thinking and even develops our problem solving ability. Children with learning problems experience difficulty while learning this subject. They struggle while comprehending & solving the word problems. Their issues of learning formulas and making things in order of operations is hard to define. Children with mathematical deficit experience difficulty while comprehending mathematical concepts & formulas and struggle semantic memory retrieval (Burny and Desoete, 2012). They battle each single day with basic calculations. They demand extra effort in understanding time, directions, money related work. Have difficulty in keeping scores of games & matches. Children with mathematical disability experience conceptual problem while analyzing, thinking abstractly and performing reasoning (Hartmann, 2007).

Understanding nonverbal cues are tricky & complex. Many children with learning disability struggle comprehending these cues. These children have trouble in adjusting to new situations, take time to adapt new changes in their life. They lack interest in activities which demand lots of coordination & organization. All those skills which are associated with rote learning & remembering got deficit. Comprehending meaning from text and thinking out of box is

difficult for them, usually they prefer things to be simple and easy.

Procuring organizational skills keep us focused and managed towards achieving goal. All those having this deficit have challenging life. Children with this disorder complained about inability to perform activities that require sequential order, meeting deadlines and following schedules. These children usually experience problem of distraction, lack of coordination and time management skills. Moreover, they are challenged with understanding and following directions. (Student Advising and Learning Center, 1992). The hard task for them is to arrange things, set priorities and manage time for themselves. Children with learning problems experience difficulty in solving a task, organizing activities, making corrections and approaching towards conclusion (Kohli, Malhotra, Mohanty, Khehra & Kaur, 2005).

Many a times, children with learning disability fail to interpret social behavior of others. Undergoing this challenge they experience inability to interpret their own environment as a consequence react inappropriately. Most of the time these children misunderstood situation and comprehend different meaning with incorrect interpretation.

Many children experiencing learning disability have deficit of audio processing. They experience trouble in understanding what they hear and making differences in sound. They also have difficulty in comprehending meaning from sounds. They require frequent repetition and still have to struggle in remembering what they heard. Because the attention–concentration is poor, the child may need many repetitions in order to process the information (Kohli, Malhotra, Mohanty, Khehra & Kaur, 2005).

Problem with visual processing is also a key area of concern for learning disable children. The foremost problem of misunderstanding in analyzing and synthesizing visually presented information. These children experience inability to differentiate between

same sounding words, struggle while copying from writing board, mispronouncing the words while reading, difficulty in comprehending meaning out of what they read and figuring out what is there in pictures & graphs. Children had inadequate copying skills (Kohli, Malhotra, Mohanty, Khehra & Kaur, 2005). These children struggle in understanding what they read despite of accurate reading and having normal nonverbal abilities. (Nation, Clarke and Marshall, 2004).

Conclusion

The study highlights significant academic challenges experienced by children with specific learning disability. Lifelong concern and its hidden nature delay its identification. With encouragement & support, if provided in right direction can give child a sense of self-worth, develop confidence and build determination to fight against tough. Parents & teachers can provide child with social & emotional tools which motivate them to overcome challenges whether it's academic or personal. By prevailing struggle against specific learning disability can help them being stronger and resilient in life. The good attitude towards SLD will give child a new hope and confidence to improve their condition and eventually get success in their life.

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